

The Primorial Coupling Constants Series and Primes– 8T

O Manor

June 29, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the second representation of the coupling constants series, i.e. spin; it is possible to construct a new and simple way that can be used for refuting other possibilities such as odd numbers as net variations, as odds are not on the prime critical line. In other words, if we assume that there are only fermions and bosons on our manifold, there exist a firm restriction regarding the possibilities of curvature orientations. Such a construction is than different from other theories that suggest an infinite variety of particles, such as string theory as an example.

Introduction

8T mainly done and analyzed by the primorial coupling constants series. The series has few representations describing the process of emission and absorption of bosons by fermions. By using the recent insight of the coupling series and bosons to be net curvature isomorphic to primes or one, located on the prime critical line, new insights and predictions can be made regarding the symmetry limitations the series imposes on which values can be associated with net curvature, i.e. outside the parenthesis .

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.3)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.31)$$

Shifting to spin representations:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N + 1$$

We can shift from first to second representation by following way, presented in the thesis:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1$$

So to proof the uniqueness of primes compared to odds or any other kind of a ring different from primes we can try associate $N_V \notin \mathbb{P}$ and construct just for means of making the point, the following term:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 9 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \mathcal{R} \quad (1.32)$$

$$\mathcal{R} \neq \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\frac{1}{2} < \mathcal{R} + \frac{1}{2} < 1 \quad (1.33)$$

Therefore, as a result we will have a total spin that is neither one-half nor one. that is against experiment and against other leading theories such as quantum field theory. The point of this short assay is that the prime is a subgroup of the real, which in a sense is much smaller and so it is imposing a restriction on the values that can be regarded as net curvature on the matric tensor. Such a framework is resembling a symmetry limitations by physical theories. In addition, when compared to string theory which allow an infinite variety of particles, some with exotic traits, the number of bosonic curvature is indeed infinite but at the same time, cannot be associated with any number. The number of options is smaller than the entire field of the reals, \mathbb{R} , as we need to take into account the spin trait given by the second representation,

Therefore, given by the term in equation (1.33) to those readers who wondered whether there should be a coupling term after the seven, with $N_V = +(9)$, the suggest answer is the following: given by spin representation considerations and by taking as an axiom that no spin between one half and one is allowed in nature, there should not be a coupling term associated with this number. Primes are imposing a strict limitation leading to a smaller infinity of bosonic ripple fields on the Einstein matric tensor.

References

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